

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

ASIMPTOTIC LINES OF ONE-SHEETED GIPERBOLOID

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Introduction

Let us consider a surface Φ which is given by equation around point P

$$\vec{r} = \vec{r}(u, v).$$

If we intersect with a plane Π passing through a point P on it, we obtain a smooth curve γ passing through point P in the intersection, which we call such a curve a plane section. A plane section γ lies in the plane Π , so its torsion is necessarily zero.

Writing the equation of the plane section in terms of the natural parameter s (i.e., arc length), and using the Frenet formulas for it (taking into account that the torsion is equal to zero), we write:

$$\begin{cases} \tau = kv \\ \nu = -k\tau \end{cases}$$

Here, τ is the unit tangent vector, ν is the unit principal normal vector, and k is the curvature of the curve γ at point $P(u_0, v_0)$. Then for second quadratic form we have

$$II(\vec{\tau}, \vec{\tau}) = (\vec{\tau}, \vec{n}) = (k\vec{\nu}, \vec{n}) = k\cos\theta$$

Here θ is the angle between the vectors \vec{n} and $\vec{\nu}$. Now, if we define γ by equation

$$\vec{\rho} = \vec{\rho}(t)$$

(where t is an arbitrary parameter), then since t is a function of s , and considering the following equalities,

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = \vec{\rho}' = \vec{\rho} \frac{ds}{dt}, \vec{\rho}'' = \vec{\rho}'' \left(\frac{ds}{dt}\right)^2 + \vec{\rho}' \frac{d^2s}{dt^2}$$

we have:

$$II(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}') = (\vec{\rho}'', \vec{n}) = \left(\frac{ds}{dt}\right)^2 (\vec{\rho}, \vec{n}) = \left(\frac{ds}{dt}\right)^2 k\cos\theta$$

We obtain following equality

$$k\cos\theta = \frac{II(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}')}{\left(\frac{ds}{dt}\right)^2} = \frac{II(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}')}{I(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}')}$$

It can be seen that the right side of this equality depends only on the vector $\vec{\rho}'$. If we take another plane section γ' other than γ and they have a common tangent (i.e., they have the same direction), then the right side of equality (1) is the same for them. Now let the the plane section be parallel to the normal vector. Therefore, equality (1) becomes:

$$k = \pm \frac{II(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}')}{I(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}')}$$

Definition 1. The number $\frac{II(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}')}{I(\vec{\rho}', \vec{\rho}')}$ obtained here is called the normal curvature of the surface Φ at point P in the direction $\vec{a} = \vec{q}'$ and is denoted by $k_a(\vec{a})$.

Thus, the absolute value of the normal curvature of the surface in the direction \vec{a} is equal to the curvature of the normal section that defines the normal vector, possibly differing in sign.

Definition 2. If $k_a(\vec{a}) = 0$ in some direction \vec{a} , then such a direction is called an asymptotic direction.

For a given vector $\vec{a} = (x, y)$, it is necessary and sufficient that $Lx^2 + 2Mxy + Ny^2 = 0$ for the direction

defining the asymptotic direction. Here, L, M, N are the coefficients of the second quadratic form.

Definition 3. If a curve γ on a surface is given by the equation $u = u(t), v = v(t)$, and its tangent vector at any point defines the asymptotic direction, then such a curve is called an asymptotic curve.

Naturally, if a straight line lies on a surface, it is an asymptotic line.

We find the asymptotic lines of a hyperbolic paraboloid. The hyperbolic paraboloid is a surface of the second order and is given by the following second-order equation:

$$z = x^2 - y^2$$

We write the parametric equations of the hyperbolic paraboloid:

$$x = u, y = v, z = u^2 - v^2$$

To calculate the first and second quadratic forms, we need to know the vectors denoted by

$$\vec{r}_u = \{1, 0, 2u\} \quad \vec{r}_v = \{0, 1, -2v\} \quad \vec{r}_{uu} = \{0, 0, 2\} \\ \vec{r}_{uv} = \{0, 0, 0\} \quad \vec{r}_{vv} = \{0, 0, -2\}$$

The coefficients of the first and second quadratic forms are

$$E = 1 + 4u^2, F = -4uv, G = 1 + 4v^2,$$

$$L = \frac{2}{\sqrt{1 + 4u^2 + 4v^2}}, M = 0, N = \frac{-2}{\sqrt{1 + 4u^2 + 4v^2}}$$

We construct the differential equation of asymptotic lines:

$$du^2 - dv^2 = 0$$

Its solutions are:

$$u_1 = t + c_1, u_2 = -t + c$$

Thus, the equations of the asymptotic lines of the hyperbolic paraboloid in space are:

$$\gamma_1: \begin{cases} x = t + c_1 \\ y = t \\ z = 2c_1t + c_1^2 \end{cases} \quad \gamma_2: \begin{cases} x = t + c_2 \\ y = t \\ z = 2c_2t + c_2^2 \end{cases}$$

Asymptotic lines of a one-sheet hyperboloid

A one-sheet hyperboloid is a quadratic surface of second order, given by the following equation:

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{a^2} - \frac{z^2}{a^2} = 0$$

Parametric equations of the one-sheet hyperboloid

$$x = \cosuchv, y = b\sinuchv, z = cshv,$$

Or, in vector form:

$$r = \{a\cosuchv, a\sinuchv, ashv\}$$

To compute the first and second quadratic forms, we calculate the partial derivatives:

$$\vec{r}_u = \{-a\sinuchv, a\cosuchv, 0\}, \vec{r}_{uu} \\ = \{-a\cosuchv, -a\sinuchv, 0\}, \vec{r}_v \\ = \{a\cosushv, a\sinushv, ashv\},$$

$$\vec{r}_{vv} = \{a\cosuchv, a\sinuchv, ashv\}, \vec{r}_{uv} \\ = \{-a\sinushv, a\cosushv, 0\}$$

The calculation of the first quadratic forms yields

$$E = \vec{r}_u^2 = x_u^2 + y_u^2 + z_u^2 = \vec{r}_{uu} \\ = x_u x_v + y_u y_v + z_u z_v = \vec{r}_{uv}^2 \\ = x_v^2 + y_v^2 + z_v^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 E &= a^2 \sin^2 u ch^2 v + a^2 \cos^2 u ch^2 v = a^2 ch^2 v, F \\
 &= -a^2 \sin u \cos u ch v sh v \\
 &+ a^2 \sin u \cos u ch v sh v = 0 \\
 G &= a^2 \cos^2 u sh^2 v + a^2 \sin^2 u sh^2 v + \\
 a^2 ch^2 v &= a^2 sh^2 v + a^2 ch^2 v = a^2 ch 2v
 \end{aligned}$$

The calculation of the second quadratic forms yields

$$L = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} x_{uu} & y_{uu} & z_{uu} \\ x_u & y_u & z_u \\ x_v & y_v & z_v \end{vmatrix}}{\sqrt{EG - F^2}}, M = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} x_{uv} & y_{uv} & z_{uv} \\ x_u & y_u & z_u \\ x_v & y_v & z_v \end{vmatrix}}{\sqrt{EG - F^2}}, N = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} x_{vv} & y_{vv} & z_{vv} \\ x_u & y_u & z_u \\ x_v & y_v & z_v \end{vmatrix}}{\sqrt{EG - F^2}}$$

$$L = -a^3 ch^3 v, M = 0, N = 2a^3 chv$$

The differential equation of the asymptotic lines is derived as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ldu^2 + 2Mdudv + Ndv^2 &= 0 \\
 -a^3 ch^3 v du^2 + 2a^2 chv dv^2 &= 0 \\
 ch^2 v du^2 &= 2dv^2 \\
 \left\{ \frac{du}{dv} \right\}^2 &= \frac{2}{ch^2 v}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int du &= \int \frac{\sqrt{2}}{chv} dv = \int \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{e^v + e^{-v}} dv = 2\sqrt{2} \int \frac{e^v dv}{e^{2v} + 1} \\
 &= \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{(e^v)^2 + 1}
 \end{aligned}$$

The intrinsic coordinate equations of the asymptotic lines can be expressed in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_1 &= 2\sqrt{2} \arctg e^v \\
 u_2 &= -2\sqrt{2} \arctg e^v
 \end{aligned}$$

The spatial equations of the asymptotic lines of the one-sheet hyperboloid can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 \gamma_1: x &= a \cos(2\sqrt{2} \arctg e^t) ch t, y \\
 &= a \sin(2\sqrt{2} \arctg e^t) ch t, z = asht \\
 \gamma_2: x &= a \cos(2\sqrt{2} \arctg e^t) ch t, y \\
 &= -a \sin(2\sqrt{2} \arctg e^t) ch t, z \\
 &= asht
 \end{aligned}$$

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